

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE SCHOOL OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article describes a methodology that defines the goals and objectives of teaching the Russian language and literature, reveals and justifies the content of the subjects studied at a certain stage of education, develops methods and techniques for the teacher and students in the educational process.*

Keywords: *teaching Russian language and literature, Uzbek language school, sociolinguistic factor, psychological factor, psychological and didactic factor, bilingualism, heuristic method.*

INTRODUCTION

The achievements of modern scientific research (primarily in psychology and psycholinguistics) make it possible to characterize the objective factors that determine the specifics of the study of the Russian language and literature in Uzbek language schools. First of all, these are sociolinguistic and psychological factors: bilingualism of learners who left Uzbek language school and study in Uzbek language groups of academic lyceums and higher educational institutions, and the originality of the figurative perception of the world based on the ethical and aesthetic ideas of the people as a result of their cultural and historical development identity. It should be noted that the psychological and didactic factor provides the simultaneous study of native, Russian and foreign languages in Uzbek language groups, which, of course, affects the development of language skills and abilities, the formation of a “sense of language”, aesthetic flair, student’s reading experience as well.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In Uzbek language schools and groups of a higher educational institution, it is important to rely on the method of comparative analysis. Reliance on linguistic scientific disciplines facilitates the solution of methodological problems associated with the learners’ perception of literature written in another language. “For the methodology of teaching the Russian language and literature in Uzbek language group, two aspects of the linguistic plan are of paramount importance: a) learners' understanding of the writer's language in its artistic function; b) mastering the linguistic means of the studied literature in order to develop learners’ speech (enriching their vocabulary, acquiring skills and abilities that help to use the means of the Russian language in accordance with a certain communicative situation”.[3]

In this case the followings are particularly important:

1) taking into account the facts that make it difficult for learners of Uzbek language school to understand Russian literature (incomplete knowledge of the Russian language; the presence of ideological and aesthetic interference due to the inconsistency of some ethical and aesthetic norms, differences in national culture);

2) taking into account factors that contribute to a deeper and more lasting study by non-Russian learners of Russian literature, creating favorable conditions for their spiritual and aesthetic development;

3) bilingualism which reveals hidden potential for the general language development of the learner's communicative personality.

The study of the Russian language and literature in Uzbek language school largely depends on how learners are taught the ability to work with a book, perceive artistic images, analyze works, highlight the most important and essential when reading the text. Acquaintance of learners with the facts of interaction between native and Russian literature provides significant assistance in overcoming the "psychological barrier" in the perception of the Russian writers' works.

An effective way for better perception of the Russian literature by Uzbek language learners is comparing the works of Russian and Uzbek writers, identifying common problems for both literatures, figurative and plot parallels, creative contacts, which makes it possible not only to rely on knowledge and skills acquired by learners in the Literature lessons, but to expand their cultural horizons, to make their aesthetic perception more flexible.

There are basic principles for using literary relationships:

1) the development of uniform guidelines regarding the analysis of images, the disclosure of the ideological content of the work, the joint selection of material necessary for the lessons of native and Russian literature, its strict separation to avoid duplication, coordinated extracurricular work;

2) careful selection by the teacher of works for classroom and extracurricular lessons, clear thinking through figurative and plot comparisons that are of learners' interest, etc. Such comparisons help to find out how learners understood the ideological orientation of reading works, show their attitude to the artistic images of Russian and native literature, activate language skills. [4]

The assimilation of linguistic facts and the formation of speech skills and abilities are more successful when a certain word or speech is used in Literature lessons. At the same time, an important form of activation of learners' mental and speech activity are exercises related to the formation of skills in expressive reading of a literary text. Teaching learners expressive reading, the teacher will also face a number of difficulties associated with the difference between the systems of Russian and native languages, which are revealed in the phonetic system of languages, in their morphological and syntactic structure.

When teaching pronunciation in the lessons of the Russian language and literature the teacher must prepare special exercises that take into account the peculiarities of the pronunciation of certain words, predict and prevent possible errors that are most often made by learners in their oral speech.

Profound understanding, comprehension of the literary work is possible with its systematic organization of vocabulary and phraseology, which enriches learners' written and oral speech. Literary texts studied in the lesson most often contain many words and word combinations that contribute to the replenishment and activation of learners' vocabulary. Educational material can be used in Russian language lessons in almost all types of exercises: selection of synonyms, antonyms, replacement of some word forms with others, written reproduction of what has been learned by heart, quoting, adding sentences, etc.

Fertile material for the development of the monologue and dialogic speech of the learner are the works of oral folk art. Proverbs, sayings, phraseological units, riddles, fairy tales enrich

learners' oral speech, make it figurative, expressive, colorful, and contribute to the expansion of their ideas about the life around them.

The experience of search, creative activity, learners acquire through the use of a heuristic method of teaching. When using this teaching method, learners are not limited to assimilation of information coming from the teacher and ready for memorization: they are actively involved in the process of cognition, although they do not solve any big holistic problem, but its individual issues. They compare and explain phenomena, make assumptions and look for facts that confirm the legitimacy of their judgments - in a word, they learn to solve these issues on their own, but the search for solutions is directed, corrected by the teacher. The teacher offers a system of interrelated questions, and a new question is posed after a sufficiently complete answer to the previous question has been given.

Heuristic method is "the method of leading questions, calculated on the fact that the learner will independently find a solution to the asked question". This general definition, accepted in dictionaries, quite clearly draws a dividing line between heuristic and research methods. On the other hand, the heuristic method borders on the reproductive method: a conversation cannot always be considered as a form of the heuristic method. In the context of teaching Russian literature to non-Russian learners, the conversation is often limited to questions that clarify only to

The legitimacy of posing such questions while reading literary work in the secondary school is beyond doubt. It is important for the teacher to make sure that the learners have a clear idea of the sequence of events, the relationship of characters, etc. A conversation on questions of a reproducing nature is a form of a reproductive teaching method. The form of the heuristic method can be, for example, a search dialog. It is always based on a certain plan, the implementation of which is designed to give a solution to certain issues of an integral cognitive task.

Being a form of a heuristic teaching method, the search dialogue becomes more complicated from class to class: it is filled with new content, it absorbs educational and cognitive tasks of a higher level of difficulty. In any search dialogue, the teacher performs the functions of a guide, and the learner acts as a follower, looking for answers to those questions of a holistic problem, to which he must eventually approach the solution.

Speaking about the fact that this dialogue can be used at any stage of studying the material of a monographic topic, it should, however, be emphasized that it is especially effective "in the process of textual analysis of works, as well as after it, when it is necessary to synthesize observations accumulated by learners" [5].

Being the embodiment of one or another method of analyzing literary works, the search dialogue fixes the actual content of the work in the memory of learners, equips them with the skills of literary criticism, albeit pedagogically transformed, analysis. With the help of a search dialogue, the recreating imagination of schoolchildren is stimulated.

The search dialogue acquires additional functions when it is accessed at the final stage, after the textual analysis of the work. With the help of this form of heuristic teaching method, not only the results of previously made observations are summed up, but also the learners' ideas that have arisen in the course of parsing a literary text are expanded and deepened. The search dialogue in this case brings learners to a qualitatively new level of comprehension of the ideological and artistic content of the work.

A conversation based on a read text (excerpt, episode) is a form of the reproductive method. Answering the teacher's questions, learners reproduce the material read in the audience (thus relying on knowledge of the text).

The importance of conversation for mastering the content and for improving learners' speech skills is difficult to overestimate. The conversation develops learners' logical thinking, contributes to the formation of a linguistic instinct and aesthetic taste, because in the course of it the wording is honed, inaccurate and primitive answers are corrected, meaningful statements are encouraged.

When formulating questions or answering them, learners independently build sentences using the acquired vocabulary and the necessary grammatical forms.

Usually, the conversation proceeds in the form of a dialogue between the teacher and learners. Less often, there is an exchange of remarks between learners asking questions and the rest of the group answering them.

Preparing for the conversation, the teacher thinks over the nature of the expected answers to the questions: will they be given by the words of the text (quoted answer), or based on the text, or will the learners formulate them themselves. The teacher's questions are subject to the following basic requirements: accessibility in content, clarity of wording, consistency, logical harmony.

RESULTS

The teacher is the facilitator of the conversation. In necessary cases, he comes to the rescue, corrects the mistakes, draws the attention of the group to them, invites the learners to supplement or correct the answer of a fellow student.

An individual approach to learners and subtle pedagogical tact are manifested during a conversation: the ability to give strong learners the opportunity to speak, to encourage shy ones, to call those who do not speak the language skillfully and tactfully to correct their mistakes. At the same time, one should take into account the preparation of the group, strive to ensure that each question is accessible, requiring a certain intellectual effort.

In the process of studying the story "Chameleon" by A.P. Chekhov in Uzbek language school for a heuristic conversation, learners can be asked the following questions:

1. What would happen if the author called his story "Two-faced"?
2. What would have happened if Khryukin had not been bitten by a dog?
3. Will the plot of the story change if the hero is not a dog, but a man?
4. How would events develop in the story if it immediately became known that the dog belongs to the general's family?

The conversation, which is based on such questions, relies heavily on the heuristic method. Preparation of answers will require learners to independently search, reflect, and argue. This will activate them, increase their interest in the literary work, and create the necessary prerequisites for the analysis of the work.

DISCUSSION

When using the research method, the role of the teacher should not be reduced to the formulation of the task, especially in the conditions of teaching literature in a language that is not native to learners. In accordance with the specific conditions of work, the teacher can not only set one or another cognitive (problem) task for the learners, but also explain what needs to be done to solve it.

In other cases, the teacher will determine ways to solve the problem together with the learners. When they acquire the necessary skills for independent research work, then it will be possible to confine themselves to the formulation of the task.

The learner's thought begins to function intensively in difficult situations, so one should not rush to help if the teacher sees that the learners, completing the task, have encountered difficulties. But if, nevertheless, the teacher decided to help the them, then his help should not result in a hint. Then the independence of solving the cognitive task will decrease somewhat, but the independence of solving the cognitive task will not be removed, and learners will approach further tasks of this type with renewed vigor.

The form of independent interpretation of literary works is the evaluation of the work. For example, learners might be asked to think about questions like: "Why does Lermontov call his love for his homeland "strange"? Why is this feeling unusual? (poem "Motherland")". If this form of interpretation is addressed in the lesson, then, naturally, they stop at small works (poems by A.S. Pushkin, S. Yesenin, stories "Thick and thin", "Death of an official" by A.P. Chekhov and etc.).

Comparisons of the original with translations into the native language of learners can be of an exploratory nature. Of course, translations made at a sufficiently high level should be involved.

CONCLUSION

The use of the research method is possible when comparing the poetic images of Russian and native poetry, searching for various correspondences, identifying the national specifics of the image, comparing similar Russian proverbs, sayings, fairy tales and folklore works of the native people.

Research tasks are such tasks that require a comparison of illustrations made by different artists for the same work (for example, a comparison of illustrations by Kukryniksov and Vereisky for the episode "Andrei Sokolov at the Camp Commandant" from the story "The Fate of a Man" by M. A. Sholokhov), as well as the compilation of verbal portraits of literary heroes. In all these cases, it is necessary to strive to ensure that learners give reasoned answers based on an analysis of the specific facts of a literary work.

REFERENCES

1. Алексеев Н.А. Личностно ориентированное обучение в школе. – Ростов-на-Дону: Феникс, 2006. – 332 с.
2. Волков И.Ф. Готовясь к урокам литературы. – М., 2008. – 191 с.
3. Кудашева З.К., Магдиева С.С. Методика обучения литературы: Учеб. пособие для студентов ВОУ. – Т.: АЛОКАЧИ, 2008. – 228 с.
4. Магдиева С.С, Лагай Е.А. Современные педагогические технологии на уроках русского языка и литературы: Учеб. пособие для учителей общеобразовательных школ Узбекистана. – Т., 2021. – 146 с.
5. Смелкова З.С. Педагогическое общение: Теория и практика учебного диалога на уроках словесности. – М.: Флинта, 1999. – С. 187.